

NON-DESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF
CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS WITH
OPTICALLY GENERATED THERMAL WAVES

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ABSTRACT

Photothermal wave analysis is a new method well suited for non-contacting and non-destructive inspection of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP). The reason is that these materials have high optical absorption coefficients and higher thermal conductivities than other polymers. Results of our experiments are: The thermal wave data show a good correlation with the Young's modulus for high modulus fibres. It is possible to measure the fibre content with an accuracy of up to nearly 1 %. Change and inhomogeneity of the material properties in the form of blowholes, cracks, and insertions can be detected up to more than 0.125 mm depth. Thermal waves also allow to monitor in situ the curing process of carbon fibre prepregs.

INTRODUCTION

As CFRP are materials for applications in air and space industries, the inspection by using non-destructive methods is of great practical interest. However, every non-destructive testing method, as ultrasonics, radiography, acoustic emission, and thermography can only show specific kinds of defects in CFRP. Each method on its own gives limited information on the material quality. The intention of our work is to complete the field of non-destructive testing of CFRP by using the remote method of thermal wave analysis.

Thermal waves as a dynamical process of heat propagation are being used since Angström's work /1/. The basic idea is that

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Fig. 1. Thermal wave propagation in a semi-infinite solid

a temperature oscillation propagates in a solid like a heavily damped wave. The thermal diffusivity is calculated from phase difference measurement in this wave field. For illustration, Fig. 1 shows the temperature oscillation $\Theta(z, t)$ as a function of distance z from the plane surface of a solid where a sinusoidal oscillation with magnitude Θ_0^* and angular frequency ω is applied at the surface ($z=0$). The local oscillation has a phase-lag of φ with respect to the origin, where μ is the thermal diffusion length with thermal diffusivity a . The phase increases linear with z . At a distance $z = \mu$ the phase shift φ is 1 rad = 57 deg. Magnitude A decays exponentially and even faster in a spherical thermal wave.

A thermal wave can be generated in a remote way by periodical deposition of optical energy, e. g. a modulated laser beam focused to the sample surface. In that case z is the distance from the laser focus which can be a spot of some μm size. Various methodes can be used to observe the temperature oscillation /2/. We prefer photothermal detection based on the modulation of thermal infrared radiation /3/. This remote method allows to observe the temperature oscillation in a small spot (size about $80 \mu\text{m}$, depending on infrared optics). The offset between the "laser spot" and "detector spot" corresponds to z in Fig. 1.

The experimental equipment allowing for this remote thermal wave analysis is shown in Fig. 2. The beam of a laser is modulated and focused on the sample. A spot nearby is ob-

served by the infrared detector (dashed dotted lines), the offset z can be adjusted by shifting the infrared optics. The detector signal is analysed with respect to A and φ by a lock-in amplifier.

Fig. 2. Experimental arrangement for remote thermal wave inspection

One kind of experiments is to observe the signal as a function of this offset z . Then the slope of the obtained $\varphi(z)$ curve ("profile") will give the thermal diffusion length (if z is larger than the spot sizes). Instead of observing the thermal wave profile one can perform another kind of experiments where at a constant offset z the signal phase φ is monitored while the sample is shifted in a raster-like fashion. Phase angle changes then reveal local variations of thermal diffusivity that may be caused by imperfections. Results of both - profiles and line scans - will be described.

Photothermal wave inspection of glass fibre reinforced plastics have been performed previously by Busse and Eyerer /4/. Ingelhart et al. used mirage effect detection of thermal waves to investigate CFRP /5/. Tittmann et al. generated thermal waves by ultrasonics /6/. They detected different degrees of porosity in CFRP. Our work reports on photothermal CFRP inspection. The material is well suited for this technique since its black colour allows for high efficiency and spatially confined deposition of optical energy, while its large thermal diffusivity allows for offsets that are larger than the spot sizes.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Carbon fibres show in their elementary structure graphite layers due to the sp^2 -hybridization of the electron or-

bitals. The mobility of the π -electrons in this structure causes the high electrical and thermal conductivity along the graphite-layers. YOUNG's modulus and strength based on the δ -bonds are directly influenced by the orientation of this crystal structure with respect to the fibre axis. The increase of the YOUNG's modulus correlates with the increasing degree of this orientation. The structure of graphite layers can be analysed by high resolution transmission electron microscopy and by X-ray diffraction. This fact was investigated by photothermal wave analysis. We used therefore some unidirectional prepregs with different fibres, however with the same resin.

Fig. 3. Identification of various High Modulus Fibres: Phase angle φ as a function of the distance z (offset) between the laser focus and the detector spot. The offset was orientated along (||) and perpendicular (\perp) to the fibres in the UD-prepreg.

Fig. 3 presents the results for high modulus prepregs. The orientation of the offset was along and perpendicular to the fibres, respectively. For the offset along the fibre the slope of the profile decreases with the increase of the YOUNG's modulus (M 30, M 40, M 50). This is the consequence of the higher thermal diffusivity for fibres with increasing YOUNG's modulus. The slope change of the profile for the orientation with the offset perpendicular to the fibres is partly caused by the increase of thermal diffusivity perpendicular to the fibre axis. In addition, with a finite size of the detector spot, the signal is a superposition of thermal wave paths which have also components along the fibres, although the detector is moved perpendicular to the fibre orientation.

The data points in Fig. 4 correlate thermal diffusion length to YOUNG's modulus for high modulus fibres (circles) and high tensile fibres (triangles). These data points can be understood as empirical calibrations that should allow to determine YOUNG's modulus from thermal data. As the experimental reproducibility of φ is about $\pm 5\%$, this procedure can be applied successfully to high modulus fibres, but obviously not to high tensile fibres with their nearly identical thermal diffusion lengths. As an explanation for this

Fig. 4. Correlation of the thermal diffusion length with the Young's modulus of various carbon fibre types

difference, we tentatively assume that the mechanical strength of these fibres is influenced not only by the orientation of the graphite crystal structure. Also we found no detectable difference between the results for T 300 6k and T 300 12k fibres: For photothermal wave analysis the number of filament fibres in the tow is not important.

The accuracy of 5% can compete with the correlation between YOUNG's modulus and the measured electrical conductivity /7/. It seems to be possible to use photothermal wave analysis for quality-control of high modulus fibres.

The content of carbon fibre in the laminate is important for the mechanical strength. Deviation of only a few percent causes a significant change in the mechanical properties. Our aim was to determine the fibre content with thermal wave analysis.

Technical CFRP has normally a fibre volume fraction ranging from 60 % to nearly 70 %. Higher values are impossible in technically producible fibre packages. Therefore we used some samples with different fibre volume fractions below this range.

Fig. 5. Phase angle increase as a function of the offset between the detector spot and the laser spot at a modulation frequency of 10 Hz

Fig. 5 shows how the fibre volume fraction affects the thermal wave profiles for offsets perpendicular to the fibre orientation. An increase of fibre content affects the thermal wave profiles in a way similar to Fig. 3. The reason is the decrease of the thermal diffusion length with increasing fibre content, while the size of the detector spot is unchanged. Therefore the thermal wave signal is averaged over contributions with larger phase angles thereby giving a larger phase angle sum. From the volume content depending phase angle data in Fig. 5 one finds that up to the fibre volume content of 45 % the thermal diffusivity is characterized by the resin. For low contents the fibres have nearly no contact with each other. At higher fibre volume content, however, the thermal diffusivity is primarily determined by the fibre contacts. This result is obvious from electrical inspections performed by Altmann /8/ and from theoretical calculations of Joy /9/.

The fibre volume content can be determined by local point measurements, but the result can be influenced by local inhomogeneities. Linescans or rasterscans are necessary to determine the integral values of the fibre content. Using these averaging measurements one finds agreement with manufacturer data. The accuracy of the result decreases with increasing fibre content: For fibre contents below 45 % the accuracy is better than 1 % and about 2 % above 45 %. These thermal wave experiments can compete with other methods to determine the fibre content. Linescans should be perpendicular to the fibre orientation in order to reduce the influ-

ence of local accumulation of fibres and resin. The values of the fibre content averaged this way can be used to estimate the mechanical strength.

Depth range in our experiments is one laminate layer (0.125 mm) at the modulation frequency of 10 Hz. Within this range defects (e.g. blowholes, cracks, inhomogeneity, and insertions) can be detected by thermal waves.

The linescans of Fig. 6 and 7 show the characteristic influence of two different insertions. The insertions were made between the first and second laminate layer. In Fig. 6 the inserted material has a smaller thermal diffusivity (PTFE) and in Fig. 7 a higher thermal diffusivity (aluminium) than CFRP. In both cases the signal magnitude is reduced by the insertions. However, the phase angle changes have opposite signs. This difference can be interpreted in terms of thermal wave reflection with different boundary

Fig. 6. Change of phase and magnitude for a local PTFE-insertion

conditions. From this result we conclude that besides finding the region and the size of inserted material it is possible to get information on the thermal conductivity in relation to the surrounding material.

Fig. 7. Change of phase and magnitude caused by an aluminium-insertion

We further investigated the curing process of carbon fibre preregs. The curing processes were performed at no pressure. To avoid local prepreg overheating by laser power, we moved the sample forth and back. This way the influence of the higher temperature to the curing could be neglected. Another advantage of this motion was the averaging process over local inhomogenities. The influence of three different temperature cycles on the same type of prepreg is shown in Figure 8. At the beginning, both phase angle $\Delta\phi$ and amplitude A increase. This fact characterizes the curing process. At higher temperature cycles the process is faster and therefore the phase angle decreases more rapidly. During the post-curing process the phase angle decreases while the amplitude increases. Such experiments were performed with similar results on different prepreg materials at different curing conditions.

Fig. 8. Phase and magnitude for different temperature curves during the curing process of a epoxy prepreg

CONCLUSION

It was demonstrated that the method is suited to estimate YOUNG'S modulus from the thermal properties detected in a non-destructive and remote way. There is also a good correlation between the thermal wave signal and the volume fibre fraction. It is possible to inspect inhomogenities, such as cracks, insertions, and delaminations in regions at a maximum distance of 0.125 mm below the surface. Thermal wave analysis seems to offer a good possibility to monitor the curing process of CFRP-prepregs.

From the results we assume that thermal wave analysis has a good chance to become a tool for quality-control of CFRP.

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